
**Genomic Characterizations, Variant Analysis, Phylogenetic Tree and
Structural Patterns of SARS-CoV-19: A Comparative Study**

A Project Presented by

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Abstract:

SARS-CoV-2 is a new coronavirus that has spread globally, infecting approximately 108 million people, and was declared a pandemic by the WHO. We provide here bioinformatics, evolutionary analysis of 13 available sequences of its genome with the aim of mapping genome structural variations. SARS-CoV-2 variants from Egypt, KSA, USA, Germany, and China were provided from NCBI. Here, we report the detection of variants within the genome of these strains. Multiple sequence alignment analysis using biopython tools was performed between these sequences and the NCBI data for the SARS-CoV-2 coronavirus to identify amino acid variations. We noticed that the Genome extracted from KSA poses the largest number of variations compared to the Reference Sequence, Our results may help to predict the virulence of different strains of Covid -19 and its degree of infectivity among different populations.

Introduction

The Severe Acute Respiratory Syndrome Coronavirus 2 (SARS-Cov-2) is a newly identified β -coronavirus that was reported as a pandemic by the World Health Organization (WHO) on March 11, 2020 (Pal et al., 2020; Huang et al., 2020). SARS-CoV-2 genome size varies from 29.8 to 29.9 kb. It is an enveloped, positive-sense RNA virus that was detected in humans and other mammals (Yadaf et al., 2020). Phylogenetic analysis of 160 complete genomes of SARS-Cov-2 isolated from different countries identified three main variants (A, B, and C) based on variabilities in their amino acid sequence [3]. The closest virus phylogenetically to SARS-CoV-2 is a coronavirus isolated from the horseshoe bat (Bat CoV RaTG13) with an overall genome sequence identity of 96.2%, which is higher than that of SARS-CoV (<80%) (Ieko et al., 2020 and Rehtoric at al., 2020). Although such analysis helped somewhat in tracing routes of infections, we are still in high demand for more cases to be compared to clarify the impact of different variants on viral pathogenicity.

The genome of SARS-Cov-2 consists of 11 genes with 11 open reading frames (ORFs). The 5' region comprises an open reading frame (ORF1ab) encoding ORF1ab polyproteins, while the 3' one comprises genes encoding structural proteins including surface (S), envelope (E), membrane (M), and nucleocapsid (N) proteins.

ORF1 ab consists of two-third of the entire genome and produces after proteolytic cleavage two polyproteins, pp1a and pp1ab that are cleaved into 16 nonstructural proteins (NSP 1 - NSP 16) [1]. NSP 3 is characterized as a multifunctional protein, acting as viral protease and inhibiting interferon responses (**Pal et al., 2020**). The NSP 12 is an RNA-dependent RNA polymerase (RdRps), a major enzyme in the replication and transcription of the SARS-Cov-2 genome (**Rehtoric et al., 2020**). NSP 14 is shown to have an exonuclease activity with proofreading function; it has been reported that any variant in this protein will make the genome of this SARS-CoV-2 strain prone to high mutational changes [4]. Moreover, scientists demonstrated that a stable super complex is produced from the NSP 7 and NSP 8 with NSP 12 (**Mousavizadeh and Ghasemi, 2020**). All these proteins will assist in the transcription fidelity of the virus.

ORF2 encodes the spike proteins (S) [**Hulswit et al., 2016**]]. This glycoprotein has two subunits, a globular S1 subunit that contains the receptor-binding domain (RBD) whereas the S2 subunit has the domain involved in fusion (**Khailany et al., 2020**). It is highly established that the spike proteins mediate the entry of SARS-Cov-2 into human cells through receptors on the host cell membrane. Mutations affecting the S protein will induce perturbations in the virus entry. Therefore, these glycoproteins were the target of vaccine investigations. On the other side, structural proteins mostly prone to the host immune response could be an excellent candidate for the therapeutic study, yet nonstructural components play as well an important role in virus-host interactions (**Sheikh et al., 2020**). Among these categories, ORF3a encodes an ion channel protein inducing caspase 1 activation and the maturation of IL-1 β and hence triggering a strong inflammatory response. Recently, SARS-CoV-2 was demonstrated to induce cytokine storms of the host cells often culminating in severe symptoms leading to death (**Yoshimoto, 2020; Abou-Hamdan et al., 2020**).

ORF3a, ORF6, ORF7, ORF8, and ORF10 encode accessory proteins. These protein groups possess high variability in their sequence. (**Liu et al., 2014; Song et al., 2019**).

The 2020 pandemic caused by SARS-CoV-2 is still out of control despite countermeasures taken worldwide. Therefore, we are still in need of a better understanding of the genome variability and the evolution of this virus through meticulous research. The purpose

of this study is to investigate the different genomic variants found in Egyptians infected with SARS-CoV-2 in comparison to other variants detected in USA, KSA, Germany, and China patients. Our data may provide new evidence to understand the origins of the variation and their reflection on different viral products' functionality. This may shed light on the great variation in people's responses to viral infection as well as defining the causes of symptoms exacerbation among particular patients.

Material and Methods

SARS-CoV-2 sequences were fetched from NCBI viral databases. by Entrez in biopython package and saving the sequence records by using SeqIO as a fasta format for alignment purposes.(**Accession number as follow:** Egypt: MT814698, MT994933, MT905421, MW504615, MW451245, USA: MT482145, MW570889, Germany: MT582474, MT582498, KSA: MT630421, MT755899, China: NC_045512, MT079843.)

For this study, we obtained **13** complete genomic sequences of Egyptian SARS-CoV-2 strains, **5** from each of Egypt, 2 from Germany, USA, China, and KSA from the NCBI. Multiple Sequence Alignment was carried out using **the Clustal W** software package. The ClustalW program of the MEGA software (7.0.14) was used to conduct multiple sequence alignment. Clustal W can read inputs of nucleotide and amino acid sequences in formats such as a2m/Fasta, Clustal, msf, phylip. selex, Stockholm, and Vienna (Lockman et al., 2020). Aligned sequences were compared against the reference-based assembly (**NCBI Reference Sequence: NC_045512.2** 'China reference (Wang et al., 2020)' to assure consistency of the results.

The NCBI sequences we collected were aligned to the reference viral sequence using the python script by importing the Bio.Application Package, we were able to identify the variation in nucleotide sequence between genomes and the reference sequence using python script where the output file of python is parsed to extract the variations of the five selected genomes(USA Mt482145, German MT582498, KSA MT630421, Egypt MT814698, and Egypt MT814698) from the 13 previously used compared to Reference Sequence (NC_045512.2)then a loop is created to iterate over the Reference Sequence and each of the five at the same time

using itertools package. The same tool is used to extract the conserved regions and their location in a file to be further analyzed according to the functionality.

Phylogenetic Tree analysis

A phylogenetic tree is a diagram that represents evolutionary relationships among organisms. The pattern of branching in a phylogenetic tree reflects how species or other groups evolved from a series of common ancestors. Clustalw program after performing multiple sequence alignment (MSA) returns output file has dnd extension. Phylo module from the Biopython package reads the dnd file and easily constructs the phylogenetic tree.

GC content analysis and percentage of the chemical constituents (C, G, T, and A)

we write a python script with the following specifications:

1. It takes the full path to a fasta file
2. It writes one line on the standard out for each fasta record
 - The line consists of two values, separated by a space: the sequence id, and the percent GC / percentage of the chemical constituents

Variant analysis

The protein-encoding genes of the genome of 2019-nCoV were predicted by the online servers of GeneMarkS (<http://exon.gatech.edu/GeneMark/genemarks.cgi>) and ORF finder (<https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/orffinder/>) with a manual check.

All of the scripts used to do previous are provided in the Final_Project.py file.

Results

The results of the alignment using CLustalW showed that the total alignment length is 29915. We extracted using Python3.0 the conserved region to find they are in total 85 among the 13 genomes we fetched. the percentage of the total length of conserved nucleotides to that of the whole alignment length is ~93.8%. By viewing the Reference sequence, we observed the regions with their function and found that ~57.6% of the conserved region lies in the ORF1ab which is expected as the open reading frame occupies two-third of the whole genome.

However, we found that the S region coding for the surface proteins from which the spike protein 10 conserved region in total which is ~11.7% of the total conserved regions of the alignment length. Figure (1) shows the distribution of the conserved regions in the most remarkable genome regions.

After we extracted the variants from each genome of the following Geographical regions (USA M482145, Germany MT582498, KSA MT630421, Egypt MW451245, and MT814698) using python script we found that: The highest number of variants are in the genomes isolated from KSA MT630421 (17 variant) as shown in table 1 which consist 51.5% of variants found, followed by the genomes isolated from Egypt MW451245 and MT814698 where we found 8 and 7 variants respectively we reported in Table 1 one of the genomes as the variation is completely the same incorporating ~24% of variants; The third one is the genome isolated from USA MT482145 which accumulates 18.2% of variants(6 variants) as displayed in table 1, the least number of variants was found in the genome isolated from Germany possessing only 2 variants and only incorporating ~6% of the total variants identified. we summarized results in Figure(2)

Table (1): Variations (SNPs) in different countries.

Egypt (MW451245) 8 variants	USA (MT482145) 6 variants	KSA (MT630421) 17 variants	Germany (MT582498) 2 variants
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> → 252 C=>T → 3048 C=>T → 14419 C=>T → 18888 C=>T → 19017 G=>T → 23414 A=>G → 25574 G=>T → 26746 C=>T 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> → 6038 C=>T → 10247 A=>G → 11094 G=>T → 14816 C=>T → 17258 T=>C → 26155 G=>T 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> → 252 C=>T → 929 A=>T → 2458 G=>T → 3048 C=>T → 14419 C=>T → 18888 C=>T → 22455 C=>T → 23414 A=>G → 25562 T=>C → 25574 G=>T → 26746 C=>T → 28865 C=>T → 29552 C=>T → 29866 T=>WTWCMTWTW → 29867 G=>RGR → 29868 G=>R → 29869 T=>WGS AW 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> → 1451 G=>A → 2902G=>A

After we constructed the phylogenetic tree as shown in figure (3) below, the phylogenetic tree shows that the 13 genome sequences are closely related to each other except for the Egyptian (MW451245) sequence that has a large branch length where the lengths indicate genetic change i.e. the longer the branch, the more genetic change (or divergence) has occurred.

Figure (3) shows the Phylogenetic Tree of the 13 tested/ aligned genomes

GC content analysis and percentage of the chemical constituents (C, G, T, and A)

The output files of our python script that used to calculate GC content and percentage of the chemical constituents showed that the GC content or even percentage of the chemical constituent is similar over the 13 genome sequence. We create a pie-chart to represent the GC content in only 4 genome sequences (M482145, MT582498, MT630421, and MW451245).

Figure (4) shows that the GC content of the four genomes is the same taking the same percentage

In Table (2) we mapped the SNP we extracted from the Egyptian genome MT814698

Locus of nucleotide variation (SNP)	MW451245 (Egypt) Genome length (29793 bp)	NC_045512 (China) Genome length (29793 bp)	Regions of similarities between the two genomes
252 C=>T	mat_peptide 181..818 product="ORF1ab polyprotein" product="nsp2"	5'UTR 1..265 gene="ORF1ab"	dissimilar
3048 C=>T	mat_peptide 2680..8514 gene="ORF1ab" product="nsp3"	3048 C=>T mat_peptide 2720..8554 gene="ORF1ab" product="nsp3"acidic (Ac), predicted phosphoesterase, papain-like proteinase, Y-domain, transmembrane domain 1 (TM1), adenosine diphosphate-ribose 1"-phosphatase (ADRP) protein_id="YP_009725299.1"	similar
14419 C=>T	mat_peptide join(13402..13428,13428..16196) gene="ORF1ab" product="RNA-dependent RNA polymerase"	mat_peptide join(13442..13468,13468..16236) gene="ORF1ab" product="RNA-dependent RNA polymerase" protein_id="YP_009725307.1"	similar
18888 C=>T	mat_peptide 18000..19580 gene="ORF1ab" product="3'-to-5' exonuclease"	mat_peptide 18040..19620 gene="ORF1ab" product="3'-to-5' exonuclease" note="nsp14A2_ ExoN and protein_id="YP_009725309.1"	similar
19017 G=>T	mat_peptide 18000..19580 gene="ORF1ab" product="3'-to-5' exonuclease"	mat_peptide 18040..19620 gene="ORF1ab" product="3'-to-5' exonuclease" produced by pp1ab protein_id="YP_009725309.1"	similar
23414 A=>G	gene 21523..25344 gene="S"/codon_start=1 product="surface glycoprotein" protein_id="QMP97386.1"	gene="S" 21563..25384 protein; spike protein" product="surface glycoprotein" protein_id="YP_009724390.1"	similar
25574 G=>T	gene 25353..26180 gene="ORF3a" codon_start=1 product="ORF3a protein" protein_id="QMP97387.1"	gene 25393..26220 gene="ORF3a" product="ORF3a protein" protein_id="YP_009724391.1"	similar

Discussion

Comparative analysis of genome sequences of SARS-CoV-2, from different worldwide isolates, revealed new variants that could provoke severe symptoms in different population. Here we describe 33 variants investigated from 5 sequenced SARS-CoV-2 genomes, identified from individuals being present in Egypt as well as the USA, Germany, KSA in comparison to the reference genome.

A script in Python (Python Software Foundation, Wilmington, United States of America) to extract the conserved regions, gaps, and variant regions between the genome variants and the reference genome was designed (Project_final.py). Nucleotide variants in the coding regions were searched for corresponding encoded proteins. The most common variants were shown in table (1 and 2). These variants include ORF3a, ORF1ab, NSP3a, RNA polymerase, spike proteins, and exonucleases.

From tables shown in the supplement, most of the Covid-SARs-2 genomes length alignment showed a 93.8% conserved region. This implies that the virus origins were the same and start from one point. This will necessitate further explorations to follow the route of virus transmission.

Searching for proteins belonging to variation locus found in this study is known as Protein mapping done by searching NCBI tools (<https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/sars-cov-2/>) and recorded ref seq databases that showed proteins encoded by the locus of nucleotide variation on the virus genome. Among the analyzed sequences in our study, these encoding proteins namely, NSPs, NSP2, NSP3, RNA polymerase, Spike protein, and exonuclease have shown many single nucleotide polymorphism (SNP) variations (shown in tables 1 and 2). It is interesting to note that these variations found here in the Egypt sequence are also abundant in KSAAs shown in table1. Point mutations or SNPs have great implications for the target drug binding and receptor binding (Puty et al., 2019). Predominantly, the mutations were also found in the different vital proteins of SARS-CoV-2 (spike glycoprotein, Nsp2, RNA polymerase, and others). The biological role of ORF1ab in SARS-CoV-2 is supposed to be clinically significant as this virus part spans two-third of the virus genome. It is transcribed into a multiprotein, which therein is divided into several nonstructural proteins (NSP1-NSP16) In one study, NSP3 has 34 variations (20 missense, 13 interchangeable, and 1 framework-shift) (Khailany et al., 2020). Wang and coworkers (2020) have recently identified 13 variation sites in SARS-CoV-2 ORF1ab, S, ORF3a, ORF8, and N regions. The frequencies of the Egyptian variations were also computed in other sequences from different regions including the USA, Germany, and Saudi Arabia. All mutations were similar to other countries' mutations. These variable sites in the Egyptian virus genomes were shown to be prevalent. This later study identified 204 mutations (including 131 ORF1ab, 6 ORF3a, 6 ORF7, 4 ORF8, and one ORF6) according to the genomic regions. The 131

high-frequency variations were observed in ORF1ab relative to the global population frequency (Zekri et al., 2020).

This also suggests that SARS-CoV-2 is highly vulnerable to have quick changes and mutates even during the person-to-person transmission. The rate and number of SNPs or mutations in SARS-CoV-2 within three months of outbreak underlines the complexity of virus to handle and corroborate the quick evolution of SARS-CoV-2 ((Andersen et al., 2020). Hence it is worthwhile to search if SNPs in SARS-CoV-2 could provoke more virus virulence leading to an increase in infectivity, morbidity, and mortality.

Conclusion

Genome analysis of SARS-CoV-2 variants all around the world is an area of research that currently forms a milestone in the process of finding the source of the virus evolution and vaccine development, using powerful programming language to assess in the analysis process may enhance and substantially decrease the time needed to complete Genome analysis process. In this process we used Python Script to extract the variants between 13 isolated genomes and Aligned the sequence using ClustalW program and Phylo package to build the Phylogenetic tree at the end we mainly used itertools package to iterate over multiply sequence and extract conserved and SNP from them. Mapping of the Egyptian genome specifically is done to identify the similar regions to the Reference sequence so that we could tell how much is Egyptian sequence varies. Further studies are needed using a larger set of sequences focusing on Egyptian isolated genomes to contribute to the research of SARS-CoV-2 in our country.

Contribution

All of the group members have shared in the project equally, and we'd like to be graded the same without any discrimination.

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